

Sample 29a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0025
{Si}	52.9
{Fe}	16.2
{Al, Si}	8.0
{Ca}	2.8
{Si, Ca LoP}	2.2
{Al, Si, Ca}	1.9
{Si, Fe}	1.8
{Na, Al, Si}	1.7
{Al, Si, K}	1.2
{Si, Ca HiP}	1.2
{Cl}	0.9
{S, Ca}	0.8
{Mg, Si}	0.8
{Na, Si, Cl}	0.8
{Cl}	0.5
{Ca, Fe}	0.5
{Mg, Ca}	0.5
{Na, Si}	0.5
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.4
{Si, K}	0.4
{Si, Cl}	0.3
{Al}	0.3
{Si, S, Ca}	0.3
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
{Ti}	0.2
{Mg, Fe}	0.2
{P, Ca}	0.2
{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{Si, Ca, Ti}	0.1
{Mn}	0.1
{Mg, Si, Fe}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.8
Pellet	2.3
Ore preparation undifferentiated	7.4
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.1
Ore / hot metal	1.0
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	1.3
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.8
Desulph slag	0.2
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.4
Olivine flux	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	18.2
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	2.2
Carbon rich - other	4.9
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	1.6
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.1
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.4
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	46.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	8.5
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.3
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.4

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	11.6
Site - ore / hot metal	1.0
Site - slag	2.8
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.5
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.6
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	18.2
Site - carbon-rich other	2.2
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	4.9
Urban; rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	2.3
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	46.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	8.5
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.4

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 29b

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0330
	{Si}	52.3
	{Fe}	12.7
	{Al, Si}	7.9
	{Ca}	3.5
	{Na, Al, Si}	3.2
	{Mg, Si}	1.9
	{Si, Fe}	1.6
	{Al, Si, K}	1.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	1.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.4
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.2
	{Cl}	1.2
	{Na, Si, Cl}	1.1
	{Cl}	0.8
	{S, Ca}	0.8
	{Na, Si}	0.7
	{Ca, Fe}	0.5
	{Si, Cl}	0.5
	{Mg, Ca}	0.4
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.4
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.4
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.3
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.3
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.2
	{S}	0.2
	{Al, Ca}	0.2
	{Na, Al, Si, Ca}	0.2
	{Mg, Fe}	0.2
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Na, Si, Cl, Ca}	0.1
	{Na, Al, Si, Cl}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.9
Pellet	1.9
Ore preparation undifferentiated	4.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.4
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.4
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.1
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.1
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.2
Olivine flux	1.2
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.6
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	15.5
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.4
Carbon rich - other	5.2
Cement or BOF converter	1.7
Cement	0.4
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.1
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.5
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	50.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	10.1
Misc silicates including natural	0.1
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.3
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	1.9

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	8.0
Site - ore / hot metal	1.4
Site - slag	1.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	1.4
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.6
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	15.5
Site - carbon-rich other	1.4
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	5.2
Urban; rarely site - slag	1.7
Urban	1.0
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	50.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	10.1
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.1
Unknown	0.3
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	1.9

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 29c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	1.9
Pellet	3.1
Ore preparation undifferentiated	4.3
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	1.5
BOF converter slag	0.1
BOF converter slag slopping	0.2
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.4
Desulph slag	0.4
Ca-aluminate slag	0.2
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Olivine flux	0.4
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.5
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.1
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	18.9
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.6
Carbon rich - other	3.1
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	1.3
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.2
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	50.1
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	10.7
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.1
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.5

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	9.3
Site - ore / hot metal	1.5
Site - slag	1.2
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.6
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.5
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.1
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	18.9
Site - carbon-rich other	1.6
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	3.1
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	1.4
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	50.1
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	10.7
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.1
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.5

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels